

V International Forum on Teacher Education

EDITORIAL: DEVELOPING TEACHER COMPETENCES

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This special edition presents a snapshot from around the world of the current state of the researches devoted to personal and professional development of teachers. The rapidly changing world entails a fundamental change in the mission of education - from translations of knowledge and skills to the industry of opportunities (motives, actions, meanings). This requires a person to continuously produce new knowledge, flexible and adaptive thinking. In this regard, in the 21st century, teacher education occupies a special place, since it develops the foundations for the success of the educational system as a whole. Therefore, in the last two decades, reform processes in teacher training have developed with varying degrees of intensity in many countries of the world.

These transformations are described in the works of leading Russian and foreign researchers in this field who participated in the V International Forum on Teacher Education held on 29-31 May, 2019 in Kazan federal university (IFTE-2019) (<http://ifte.kpfu.ru/en/home-page/>). In this special issue, contributors from different countries give the analysis of values and priorities within the field of modern teacher education; issues related to modernization processes and contents of teacher education including the requirements of a competency-based approach; educational technologies used for personal and professional early-career teacher development; integration of pedagogical university education and classical (non-pedagogical) higher education for the effective development of teacher competence; issues related to improvement processes within the system of continuing (lifelong) teacher education. The Forum was organized in partnership with the Russian Educational Research Association (RERA), Educational Studies Association of Ireland (ESAI), International Janusz Korczak Association (IKA) with support from World Education Research Association (WERA), Association for Teacher Education in Europe (ATEE) and International Association of Educators (INASED). More than 600 delegates from 132 Russian and 74 overseas universities and research centres participated in the Forum (including scientists and practitioners from Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Cuba, Germany, India, Italy, Kazakhstan, Namibia, Poland, Portugal, Serbia, Slovenia, Sweden, Spain, Trinidad and Tobago, Turkey, the UK, and the USA). Over the years Forum has grown to be one of the biggest conferences in the field of education in Eastern Europe and post-Soviet countries. Annually distinguished scholars, experts and practitioners from all over the world take part in the discussions and share their experience and insights into teacher education creating an 'academic bridge' between Russian and overseas educators. During the Forum three International sub-conferences were held: International Conference

“Continuing teacher education: new concepts and technologies”, International Conference “Early-career teachers: induction and professional development” and International Conference “Research-based teacher education”. 580 papers on a range of various educational themes were presented at the Forum. Researchers shared their views and research results on the issues of modernization and development of the content of teacher education. They discussed questions related to a new type of teachers and their professionalism, methodology, theory and practice of research in teacher education. Key issues of teacher competence development within the current information education environment and other essential topics related to teacher education were also touched upon at the symposiums and round tables.

It’s not by chance that the International Forum on Teacher Education is held at Kazan Federal University as it is one of the most renowned and largest Russian research centres in the field of education and psychology. The University offers 42 bachelor’s and 37 master’s pedagogical programmes. Over 10,000 students with a teacher education major are studying at KFU. Annually, over 10,000 in-service teachers complete professional development courses run by the University. KFU is one of the few universities implementing programmes in all three tiers of higher education and in all subject majors needed for modern schools. The University boasts an internationally recognised teacher education infrastructure and a unique teacher education model that combines the advantages of traditional (non-pedagogical) and pedagogical universities. Out of all Russian universities that offer teacher education programs, KFU is the only one ranked among the best universities in the world in the subject area “Education” according to the QS and THE rankings. Along with that, according to the Times Higher Education rankings, KFU heads the list of the best universities located in the Eastern Europe and post-Soviet countries in the subject area “Education”. That is one of the KFU’s key priorities in integrating Russian education research into the international scientific community.

The Special Issue includes the following 3 sections: Teacher Education and Training, Educational Environment and Management, Educational Psychology. The proposed sections are a collection of articles devoted to organizational, content, technological and methodical aspects of pedagogical education in Russia, the UK, America, Bulgaria, and Uzbekistan.

Teacher Education and Training section includes all the issues related to modern teachers’ training and their career and professional development. The collection of articles presented in this section covers the following issues: organization of lifelong learning in the system of professional training of teachers; forming readiness of master’s degree students for scientific and research activity; project management on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization; the methodological aspects of the research-based teacher education; psychological mechanisms of the development of future teachers’ professional qualities; monitoring young teachers’ readiness to innovation activity in a modern school; necessity to research risks of education digitalization for successful training of future teachers; the formation of foresight

competence as a factor in improving the quality of teacher training; pedagogical orientation of student teachers to universal values, etc.

Educational Environment and Management section includes articles that reveal the features of the educational process and its organization in Russian and foreign universities. The authors disclose such issues as: psychological and pedagogical security of educational environment in higher educational establishments as a prerequisite for successful adaptation of first-year students; educational IT environment and the problem of a foreign language teacher's information and communication competence formation; pedagogical design of creative strategies for students' self-development in the digital era; ecological problems of the region as the base for foundation of an English-speaking communicative competence; formation of youth readiness to the development of environmental volunteering at university; etc.

The articles of *Educational Psychology* section represent different views of Russian and foreign scientists and practitioners on psychological and pedagogical problems of student teaching and upbringing process. This section details the following issues: the problems of inclusive education, speech generating device as a tool supporting an improvement of communication skills of the children with autism; interrelation between character traits and coping behavior in adolescence; prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at deviant behavior in the logic of the systems theory; relationship between forecasting strategies and successful socialization in children with speech pathology; the subjective experience of mental states in individuals with deviant behavior at a forecasting situation; emotional intelligence, anxiety and aggression as predictors of destructive behaviour and offences of teenagers; psychological approaches helping migrant university students cope with depressive disorders, etc. .

We would like to thank everybody who helped to edit the publications, who wrote reviews on the articles. We send warm thanks to the members of scientific committee (PhDs and researches from Russia and other countries) who seriously checked the quality and authenticity of the manuscripts. We send special thanks to the editorial committee members who prepared this issue. We are grateful to our partners – Russian Educational Research Association (RERA), Educational Studies Association of Ireland (ESAI), International Janusz Korczak Association (IKA) with support from World Education Research Association (WERA), Association for Teacher Education in Europe (ATEE) and International Association of Educators (INASED) for their support and share of international experience as a source of innovation in improving the Russian system of teacher education.